

THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF PAN-BASED CARBON FIBRES AND NANOSTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT

Haruki Okuda^{1,2,3*}, Robert J. Young², Fumihiko Tanaka¹, Jun Watanabe^{1,3} and Tomonaga Okabe³

¹ Composite Materials Research Laboratories, TORAY Industries, Inc.,
1515 Tsutsui, Masaki-cho, Iyo-gun, Ehime, 791-3193, Japan
Email: Haruki.Okuda@nts.toray.co.jp, Web page: <http://www.toray.com>

² School of Materials, University of Manchester,
Grosvenor Street, Manchester, M1 7HS, UK

³ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University,
6-6-01, Aoba-yama, Aoba-ku, Sendai, Miyagi, 980-8579, Japan

Keywords: Carbon fibre, tensile strength, nanostructure, Raman, loop test

ABSTRACT

A new experimental technique has been developed for the clearer understanding of the tensile failure phenomena of polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibres. A major drawback of the existing loop test, which has widely been used for exploring the high strength region of carbon fibres despite its stress uncertainty, was successfully overcome using Raman band shift analysis. This enabled a quantitative tensile strength measurement at gauge lengths down to below 100 μm . The high potential of the PAN-based carbon fibres in terms of the tensile strength was confirmed experimentally. Moreover, an anomalous strength distribution was found at the high strength region, which could be related to the effect of nanostructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

PAN-based carbon fibres are now playing essential roles in a broad range of applications which include sporting and leisure, aerospace, industrial and, most recently, automotive due to their excellent performance per unit weight. Tensile strength, which is one of the most outstanding properties of the PAN-based carbon fibres, has been continuously improved mainly through the extensive efforts in reducing the fracture-initiating flaws on the basis of a linear elastic fracture mechanical (LEFM) understanding [1]. Meanwhile, considering that the nanostructures within carbon fibres have certain dimensions, it is likely that the flaw reduction, in terms of size and numbers, will eventually lead to the tensile strength being controlled essentially by the nanostructures. We therefore believe that a clearer understanding on the tensile failure phenomena, especially for the high strength region, is beneficial for the further improvements in the carbon fibre mechanical properties.

Although there have already been considerable efforts in clarifying the effect of the nanostructure upon tensile strength [2-5], the lack of sufficient experimental supports prevents them from being widely accepted as a guideline for improvements. A reliable experimental characterisation for the high strength region is essential.

It is well known that the tensile strength of carbon fibres scales with the gauge length mainly due to the statistical aspect of the fracture-initiating flaws. This allows us to access the high strength region by reducing the gauge length. However, the accessible gauge length in the single fibre tensile test (SFT) is limited by the clamp-effect [6]. It is usually longer than 5-10 mm in the case of the typical carbon fibres. Shorter gauge length can be achieved using the single fibre fragmentation test (SFFT), where the tensile strength distribution is estimated from the fragmentation behaviour of the fibres stressed in the matrix polymer using a shear-lag theory [7]. We have recently applied the SFFT for a range of the PAN-based carbon fibres [8,9]. There is, however, an intrinsic limitation that the strong fibre/ matrix interface is necessary for the accurate evaluation of the high strength region. Much shorter gauge length can be reached using the single fibre loop test [10-17] and the flexural test [18].

The use of these methods has resulted in higher apparent tensile strengths, or failure strains, than are evaluated with the normal tensile test. However, the use of unrealistic assumptions in the estimation of the tensile stress based on the beam bending theory makes these test methods semi-quantitative. Indeed, the shift of the neutral plane has been recently observed [19]. The quantitative characterisation of the high strength region is therefore still challenging.

In this study, we introduce a new experimental technique based on the loop test. The actual tensile stress at the loop top surface is evaluated using the Raman band shift. Using this new technique, the tensile strength at the short gauge length, or the high strength region, is quantitatively characterised for a series of PAN-based carbon fibres. We then attempt to understand these experimental results from a nanostructural viewpoint.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Five kinds of PAN-based carbon fibres, including TORAYCA™ T800S and the experimental fibres named CF1, CF2, CF3 and CF4, which have tensile modulus of 240-440 GPa were used in this study. The cross section shapes of these carbon fibres are essentially circular and the average diameter ranges 5.3-5.8 μm . Either no or mild surface treatments were performed after carbonisation or graphitisation to avoid any possible effect from changes in the surface structure.

2.2 Methods

Raman spectra were recorded using a Renishaw 1000 spectrophotometer equipped with a He-Ne laser source (wavelength=633 nm). The laser power was set below 3 mW in order to avoid damage associated with the heating. An objective magnification of 50 \times was chosen which gives beam spot diameter of around 2 μm . The penetration depth of the excitation beam into the carbon fibre was estimated to be less than 10 nm justifying the use of the Raman technique for evaluating the stress state at the carbon fibre surface. The loop axis was carefully adjusted so that the misalignment angle against the incident beam axis is less than 5° (Fig. 1(a-c)). Making the loop diameter smaller stepwise by pulling the two fibre ends fixed on a micrometre head, Raman spectra were recorded for each step. Independently, the stress dependences of the Raman band position were evaluated by recording Raman spectra during single fibre tensile tests of short gauge length ($L=2\text{mm}$). The stress dependence thus obtained was used to convert a Raman band shift to the tensile stress at the loop top. The fibre diameter was measured from micrographs which were recorded using a Zeiss EVO60 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Figure 1: (a) Experimental geometry, where a special care was taken to align the loop axis parallel to the incident beam axis for the accuracy, (b) top view of the looped fibre, (c) side view

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Loop top stress

The Raman spectra taken at the loop top of a T800S single fibre are shown in Fig. 2. Shown on the each spectrum is the reciprocal of the loop diameter W normalised with the fibre diameter d , which was used throughout this study for indicating the bending strain irrespective of the differences in fibre diameter. Each spectrum shows the G (1595 cm^{-1}) band and D (1340 cm^{-1}) band clearly, which represent the crystallite and amorphous parts within the carbon fibre, respectively [20]. With increasing d/W , the peak positions monotonically downshifted. This indicates that the loop top surface is under tensile stress.

Figure 2: Raman spectra measured at the loop top of a T800S single carbon fibre at different d/W . Monotonic downshift of the peak positions shows the loop top surface is under tensile stress.

Next, the actual tensile stress at the loop top was evaluated from the observed Raman band shifts. Using the stress-band shift relationship which was obtained independently, both G and D band shifts were converted to the stress σ_G and σ_D , respectively. Results are shown in Fig. 3(a), where different fibre types are shown in different colours and each fibre types contains result from 3-5 different single fibres. Regardless of the fibre type the two stress values σ_G and σ_D agreed very well. Moreover, the small scatter of the individual data points shows the sufficient accuracy in the Raman spectra analysis. For the quantitative discussion hereafter, the average value σ ($=(\sigma_G + \sigma_D)/2$) instead of the individual values was used.

Fig. 3(b) shows the tensile stress at the loop top against d/W . Only T800S and CF4 are shown for the sake of clarity. The tensile modulus is 294 and 440 GPa, respectively. The symbols represent the experimentally observed values, while the solid lines are obtained with the theoretical calculation (eq.1) based on the beam bending theory [17]. Here, E denotes the elastic modulus in the axis direction. For the theoretical calculation, the manufacturer's values of the tensile modulus were used. It was found that the calculations were always higher than the observed stress values. Note that all the preceding analyses have essentially been based on this calculation [10-16].

$$\sigma = 1.07E(d/W) \quad (1)$$

If the initial modulus is used instead of the manufacturer's value, the calculation reproduced the observed stress values at the initial slopes (see inset). Since neither compressive failure nor intensive nonlinear elasticity takes place at very small strain, it is expected that a carbon fibre deforms as an ideal elastic beam, therefore, the beam bending theory predict the actual stress correctly. Judging from

the agreement between the calculation and the experiment, the present approach using the Raman measurement can evaluate the actual stress at the loop top reasonably well. In addition, it should be noted that the different fibre type shows the different curve and the nonlinear behaviour is more significant for CF4. This probably arises from the difference in the compressive strength and the nonlinear stress-strain properties. Since it is practically difficult to calculate the stress taking all these factors into account, this present approach is essential for the quantitative study of the loop test.

Figure 3: (a) The experimentally obtained tensile strength σ_G and σ_D evaluated from the G and D band shift, respectively. For each fibre type 3-5 single fibres are tested. The colours represent different fibre types. Red: T800S, pink: CF1, purple: CF2, black: CF3, blue: CF4. (b) Tensile stress at the loop top plotted against d/W (fibre diameter/ loop diameter). Only T800S and CF4 are shown for the sake of clarity. Symbols: experimental results, Solid lines: calculated results using the manufacturer's values of the tensile modulus. Inset: initial modulus was used for the calculation (the origin magnified).

3.2 Strength distribution

The tensile strength of T800S evaluated with the loop test is shown in Fig. 4(a). The strength data, except for the two weaker breaks, were fitted well with the Weibull distribution. The Weibull scale parameter σ_0 was found to be 12 GPa and the shape parameter m 20. A statistical consideration based on the Weakest Link Theory (WLT) allowed us to estimate the gauge length of the loop test and discuss the experimental results more in detail. Fig. 4(b) shows the Weibull plot of the results obtained with the tensile test and the loop test normalised with the gauge length, which is 10 and 50 mm for the tensile test and approx. 50 μm for the loop test. It should be noted that the lower data points for the loop test results fell in the almost same line as the tensile test results without any adjustment. This indirectly validates the statistical treatment.

One of the key findings is the anomalous strength distribution at the high strength region. Similar behaviour has recently been found for the T800S with the SFFT, where the number of the fibre breaks within the single fibre composites required the bimodal Weibull distribution for the quantitative explanation [9]. It is also important to mention that the highest tensile strength experimentally observed for the T800S single fibres is 13 GPa. This suggests a considerable potential impact of flaw reduction upon the tensile strength.

Figure 4: (a) Weibull plot of the tensile strength obtained with the loop test. Symbols: experimental results, solid line: eye guide showing slopes. (b) Normalised Weibull plots. Diamond, triangle: SFT with the gauge length of 50 mm and 10 mm, respectively. Filled circle: loop test. The average gauge length of the loop test was estimated to be approx. 50 μm .

3.3 Fracture origin at the high strength region

Assuming that the fracture origin is a sharp crack, the size of the fracture origin associated with the high strength region was estimated based on the Griffith equation (eq.2). K_{IC} , F and c denotes the mode I fracture toughness, the geometrical correction factor, the crack size, respectively. Using the values of $1.1 \text{ MPa m}^{0.5}$ and 0.773 for K_{IC} and F , respectively [8], the crack size c was estimated to be c.a. 5 nm for the Weibull scale factor σ_0 of 12 GPa. It should be noted that this is quite near the dimension of the average size of the crystallite L_c , which is determined to be 2 nm for T800S [9]. Although this is only a rough estimate based on the sharp-crack assumption, it is likely that failure in the high strength region is affected by the nanostructures.

$$\sigma = K_{IC}/F(\pi c)^{-0.5} \quad (2)$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

A new experimental technique for the quantitative evaluation of the high strength region has been developed. A statistical study including the high strength region has been performed and an anomalous strength distribution was revealed. The highest observed tensile strength was 13 GPa, which suggested a considerable potential impact of the flaw reduction upon the tensile strength. We believe the precise control of the nanostructure will lead to further improvement in the tensile strength.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Whitney and R.M. Kimmel, Griffith Equation and Carbon Fibre Strength, *Nature Physical Science*, **237**(75), 1972, pp.93–94 (doi: 10.1038/physci237093a0)
- [2] G.A. Cooper and R.M. Mayer, The strength of carbon fibres, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **6**(1), 1971, pp.60–67 (doi: 10.1007/BF00550292)
- [3] M. Stewart and M. Feughelman, The fracture mechanism of carbon fibres, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **8**(8), 1973, pp.1119–1122 (doi: 10.1007/BF00632763)

- [4] C.N. Tyson, Fracture mechanisms in carbon fibres derived from pan in the temperature range 1000-2800 degrees C. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, **8**(7), 1975, pp.749–758 (doi: 10.1088/0022-3727/8/7/007)
- [5] W.N. Reynolds and J.V. Sharp, Crystal shear limit to carbon fibre strength, *Carbon*, **12**(2), 1974, pp.103–110 (doi: 10.1016/0008-6223(74)90018-9)
- [6] S. Phoenix and R. Sexsmith, Clamp effects in fiber testing, *J. Compos. Mater.*, **6**, 1972, pp.322.
- [7] T. Okabe and N. Takeda, Elastoplastic shear-lag analysis of single-fiber composites and strength prediction of unidirectional multi-fiber composites, *Compos. Part A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **33**, 2002, pp.1327–1335 (doi: 10.1016/S1359-835X(02)00170-7)
- [8] F. Tanaka, T. Okabe, H. Okuda, I.A. Kinloch and R.J. Young, Factors controlling the strength of carbon fibres in tension, *Compos. Part A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **57**, 2014, pp.88–94 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.11.007)
- [9] J. Watanabe, F. Tanaka, H. Okuda and T. Okabe, Tensile strength distribution of carbon fibers at short gauge lengths, *Adv. Compos. Mater.*, **23**(5-6), 2014, pp.535–550 (doi: 10.1080/09243046.2014.915120).
- [10] W.R. Jones and J.W. Johnson, Intrinsic strength and non-Hookean behaviour of carbon fibres, *Carbon*, **9**(5), 1971, pp.645–655 (doi: 10.1016/0008-6223(71)90087-X)
- [11] D.J. Thorne, Carbon fibres with large breaking strain, *Nature*, **248**(5451), 1974, pp.754–756 (doi: 10.1038/248754a0)
- [12] J.L.G. Da Silva and D.J. Johnson, Flexural studies of carbon fibres, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **19**(10), 1984, pp.3201–3210 (doi: 10.1007/BF00549805)
- [13] I. Krucinska, Evaluation of the intrinsic mechanical properties of carbon fibres, *Compos. Sci. Tech.*, **41**(3), 1991, pp.287–301 (doi: 10.1016/0266-3538(91)90004-9)
- [14] M. Trinqucoste, J.L. Carlier, A. Derré, P. Delhaès and P. Chadeyron, High temperature thermal and mechanical properties of high tensile carbon single filaments, *Carbon*, **34**(7), 1996, pp.923–929 (doi: 10.1016/0008-6223(96)00052-8)
- [15] H. Fukuda, M. Yakushiji and A. Wada, A loop test to measure the strength of monofilaments used for advanced composites, *Adv. Compos. Mater.*, **8**(3), 1999, pp.281–291 (doi: 10.1163/156855199X00272)
- [16] F. López Jiménez and S. Pellegrino, Failure of Carbon Fibers at a Crease in a Fiber-Reinforced Silicone Sheet, *J. Appl. Mech.*, **80**(1), 2012, pp.011020.
- [17] D. Sinclair, A Bending Method for Measurement of the Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus of Glass Fibers, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **21**(5), 1950, pp.380 (doi: 10.1063/1.1699670)
- [18] K. Naito, Y. Tanaka, J.M. Yang, and Y. Kagawa, Flexural Properties of PAN- and Pitch-Based Carbon Fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **92**(1), 2009, pp.186–192 (doi: 10.1111/j.1551-2916.2008.02868.x)
- [19] D. Loidl, O. Paris, M. Burghammer, C. Riekkel and H. Peterlik, Direct Observation of Nanocrystallite Buckling in Carbon Fibers under Bending Load. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **95**(22), 2005, pp.225501 (doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.95.225501)
- [20] F. Tanaka, T. Okabe, H. Okuda, M. Ise, I.A. Kinloch, T. Mori and R.J. Young, The effect of nanostructure upon the deformation micromechanics of carbon fibres, *Carbon*, **52**, 2013, pp.372–378 (doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2012.09.047).